

Project details

Duration: 36 months

Starting date: 1 October 2023

Call: HORIZON-CL3-2022-BM-01

Project coordinator: INDRA SISTEMAS SA (INDRA)

SMAUG team

22 organisations, including universities, SMEs, research organisations, public institutions as well as customs, are on board to achieve the maximum results and impact of the SMAUG objectives, offering their unique expertise and knowledge

SMAUG's social world

Discover the SMAUG project!

@SMAUG_EU @SMAUG_EU @SMAUG_EU

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Smart Maritime And Underwater Guardian

The SMAUG project's mission is to improve and enhance the security of ports and their entrance routes by utilising artificial intelligence (AI) and an integrated system that can provide data regarding threat detection and analysis between three main elements:

Ports security
infrastructure

Advanced underwater
detection systems

Surveillance
vessels

SMAUG has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101121129

Funded by
the European Union

Underwater detection and location will be performed by four primary methods:

Acoustic detection

where a series of hydrophones will listen for sounds emitted by small underwater vehicles and will be processed by artificial intelligence methods

Rapid sonar hull scan

used to scan ships' hulls and perform harbour floor scanning

High-resolution sonar inspection

of objects in water with poor visibility

Collective autonomous location

where a swarm of autonomous underwater vehicles will act cooperatively

SMAUG objectives

PCS and CCS systems

Information Exchange

Detection Systems

Surface and Underwater Vessel

Vessel features

AI for security

Screening Capabilities

SMAUG's Validation

SMAUG methodology

SMAUG pilots

SMAUG will showcase and validate the multiple solutions produced during the project in three project pilots.

Their outcomes will be examined in a real port environment and, more precisely, at the ports of Valencia (Spain), Elefsina (Greece), Heraklion (Greece), and Drammen (Norway).

Discover the SMAUG pilots